

U-Pb geochronology of wolframite from Polski Gradets, Bulgaria and Barruecopardo, Spain, using *in situ* LA-ICP-MS technique

*Irena Peytcheva*¹, *Stoyan Georgiev*¹, *Valentin Y. Ganev*¹, *Milen Stavrev*¹, *Fernando Tornos*²,
*Marko Holma*³

¹ Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria; E-mails: impeytcheva@gmail.com; kantega@abv.bg

² Instituto de Geociencias, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC); E-mail: f.tornos@csic.es

³ University of Oulu, Kerttu Saalasti Institute, PL 8000, 90 014 Oulu, Finland; E-mail: marko.holma@oulu.fi

U-Pb геохронология на волфрамит от Полски Градец, България и Баруекопардо, Испания с използване на *in situ* LA-ICP-MS техника

*Ирена Пейчева*¹, *Стоян Георгиев*¹, *Валентин Ганев*¹, *Милен Ставрев*¹, *Фернандо Торнос*²,
*Марко Холма*³

Abstract. This study presents U-Pb age data obtained using an *in situ* LA-ICP-MS technique applied to wolframite samples from Polski Gradets (Bulgaria) and Barruecopardo (Spain). Analytical conditions were optimized using YGX2113 (wolframite) and GJ1 (zircon) natural standard reference materials (SRMs). Applying both SRMs, very similar U-Pb age results were obtained. Furthermore, the results were within the reported age error range of the host granites and granodiorites. The tungsten mineralization at Barruecopardo was dated at 315.2 ± 5.3 Ma, while for Polski Gradets wolframite, an age of 79.0 ± 6.8 Ma was obtained. The applied technique is assessed as applicable and suitable for further direct dating of tungsten deposits.

Keywords: wolframite, LA-ICP-MS, U-Pb geochronology, CRMs, AGEMERA.

Introduction

The timing of hydrothermal deposits is an important parameter for understanding their genesis, the complex mineralization processes, and, in some cases, predicting ore deposition grades (e.g., in supergiant porphyry-copper deposits, where copper endowment correlates with the timescales of magmatic and hydrothermal activity; Virmond et al., 2024). Common dating techniques used to define the magmatic to hydrothermal stages of ore-deposit formation include U-Pb geochronology (applied to minerals such as zircon, titanite, rutile, columbite-tantalite, and Ca-series garnets, and, furthermore, to U-bearing minerals), Re-Os (used for molybdenite,

arsenopyrite, and pyrite), Ar-Ar (for K-bearing alteration minerals such as micas and feldspars; Ci-aradia et al., 2013). Among these isotopic methods, the zircon U-Pb CA-ID-TIMS technique has so far provided the highest precision. However, in some cases, the correlation with a specific magmatic event is unclear, making direct dating of the hydrothermal mineralization preferable.

In the present study, we provide data from the first application of direct LA-ICP-MS U-Pb dating on wolframite from two tungsten (W) deposits: the Barruecopardo (Spain), and Polski Gradets (Bulgaria). The *in situ* U-Pb dating technique of wolframite is described in the recent publications of Deng et al. (2019) and Yang et al. (2023); however, varia-

tions in laboratory setups and equipment necessitate preliminary methodological adaptations to achieve optimal analytical conditions. In our approach, we initially analyzed a series of wolframite standard reference materials (SRMs), which we compiled alongside dating analyses of zircon SRMs (GJ1, 91500). After optimizing the analytical conditions, we applied the dating technique to samples from the two selected deposits in Spain and Bulgaria. This work is driven by the ongoing Horizon Europe project called ‘AGEMERA: Agile Exploration and Geo-modelling for European Critical Raw Materials’, and the growing demand for critical raw materials. Among the latter, tungsten is defined as a critical and strategic raw material (Grohol, Veeh, 2023).

Geological setting and samples description

The Barruecopardo tungsten deposit, located in Salamanca (Castile and León), Western Spain, lies near the Portuguese border. Barruecopardo is one of the largest tungsten reserves in Spain, having an estimated ~10.9 million tons of ore grading ~0.45% tungsten. The area is a part of the Central Iberian Zone (CIZ) of the Iberian massif. The basement rocks are formed of two discordantly overlying Paleozoic metasedimentary units, intruded by significant volumes of Variscan granites dated between 326 and 311 Ma (Pohl, 2023). All rocks have been deformed during the Variscan orogeny, with later reactivations during the Alpine orogeny. The Barruecopardo tungsten mineralization is hosted by a peraluminous granodiorite to granite and occurs in quartz vein swarms interpreted as extensional structures formed by late brittle deformation during Variscan times. The mineralization is dominated by scheelite (CaWO_4) with only sporadic wolframite ($(\text{Fe}, \text{Mn})\text{WO}_4$). Scheelite is accompanied by arsenopyrite, and lesser amounts of pyrite and chalcopyrite (Antona et al., 1994; Pohl, 2023). The host rock is affected by pervasive potassic alteration and late phyllic alteration; the mineralization is related to the first one. Although the Barruecopardo mine closed in the early 1980s, it reopened for tungsten production in early 2019 under Saloro SLU. Samples for this study, collected in March 2024, comprise quartz veins containing wolframite, scheelite, and sulfides.

The Polski Gradets W deposit, located in central-eastern Bulgaria, lies within the southernmost reaches of the Sredna-Gora (Srednogorie) Late Cretaceous magmatic and metallogenic zone. This deposit, which was explored for tungsten as early as the 1960s and 1970s, is smaller than Bulgaria’s largest W deposit, Grancharitsa, Western Rhodopes (Popov, Popov, 2022). Tungsten occurrences

are also known in other granite-related deposits in Bulgaria, such as the Mo-Ag-Au-W-Bi-base metal deposit at Babyak (Stavrev et al., 2021). The first detailed publication by Nedjalkov (1983) described the Polski Gradets deposit as related to the granitoids of the Polski Gradets pluton that contains diorites, quartz-diorites, granodiorites, and leucogranites (Kamenov, Tarassova, 1995). The pluton is dated at 78.27 ± 0.18 Ma (ID-TIMS U-Pb on zircons) by Georgiev et al. (2012). Nedjalkov (1983) identified two W-bearing associations: quartz-wolframite veins in the peripheral zones of a small granite intrusive with greisen-like alteration, and scheelite-bearing (+ molybdenite) skarns in the contact aureole of the same granite. Subsequent studies on the mineralization provided data on the skarn mineral associations and established the following mineralization types in quartz veins: 1) early wolframite-molybdenite-scheelite-pyrite mineralization in the central parts of the pluton, 2) magnetite-hematite (\pm ilmenite, rutile) in contact with low-grade metamorphic marbles, calc-schists, and metasandstones, and 3) late sulfide mineralization with pyrite, chalcopyrite, molybdenite, and bismuthinite (\pm scheelite, gold) (Tarassova et al., 1996). The wolframite is Fe-rich (ferberite), with variable hübnerite content (MnWO_4 : 32–40 mol.% in wolframite1 and 22–26 mol.% in wolframite2) and low concentrations of trace elements such as Sc, Y, V, Ti, and Ni (Tarassov, Iliev, 1992). Samples for the present study are a quartz-wolframite vein sample provided by the Earth and Man National Museum (PG1), Sofia, Bulgaria, and a field-collected sample from former exploration sites (PG2).

Analytical procedure and methods

The mass spectrometer was preliminary adjusted and optimized in dry plasma conditions using NIST-610/612 SRM as standard. U-Pb age results were calculated using Iolite software in conjunction with the VisualAge data reduction scheme (DRS), which corrects for instrumental drift and down-hole fractionation effects. All age data are reported with 2-sigma error uncertainties unless otherwise stated. For trace element composition calculations, the SILLS data reduction program was applied. Age data diagrams were produced using Isoplot 4.15.

Results and discussion

Wolframite SRM selection

Data on available wolframite SRMs combining ID-TIMS and LA-ICP-MS analyses were published by Yang et al. (2020). We performed geochronological analyses of YGX2113, YGX2107, Sewa, and HTD using GJ1 as the primary standard under the ana-

Fig. 1. Concordia diagrams and $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ mean age of the wolframite from Barruecopardo W deposit, Spain (a–b) and Polski Gradets W-deposit, Bulgaria (c–d)

lytical conditions described above. Our concordia age for YGX2113 and YGX2107 wolframites (excluding a few discordant analyses) is 159.9 ± 4.4 Ma, suggesting its suitability as a SRM for dating wolframites of unknown age, alongside the GJ1 zircon standard. Our data on only a few analyses of Sewa are inconsistent, leading us to conclude that Sewa wolframite is unsuitable as a primary SRM. HTD wolframite revealed constant but too low U content (8–10 ppm) and an age of 318 ± 4.4 Ma, which is significantly higher than the published value of 281 ± 2.5 Ma, possibly due to the limited number of analyses. We decided to continue further investigation of HTD before potentially adopting it as a primary wolframite SRM in our GI-BAS laboratory.

Dating of wolframite from the deposits

The *in situ* U-Pb LA-ICP-MS wolframite age data from the Barruecopardo W deposit are presented in Fig. 1a–b. This dataset yields a lower intercept age at 291 ± 25 Ma (MSWD = 1.02) and a $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ Tukey's

Biweight Mean (TBM) age of 315.2 ± 5.3 Ma (95% confidence), using GJ1 as the primary standard. Using YGX2113 as the primary SRM results in an intercept age of 299 ± 21 Ma (MSWD = 1.2) and a $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ TBM age of 320.4 ± 5.0 Ma (95% conf.). A similar age was obtained by dating W-bearing rutile from the same deposit, yielding a TBM age of 314.5 ± 6.9 (95% conf.). These age data suggest that the Barruecopardo W deposit may belong to the older group of W-Sn deposits within the Iberian Sn-W metallogenic province in Spain and Portugal, associated with highly peraluminous syn- to late-kinematic mesozonal to epizonal magmatism (Borrajó et al., 2022).

The U-Pb LA-ICP-MS dating of wolframite from the Polski Gradets deposit was performed on two samples, resulting in an intercept age of 78 ± 13 Ma (MSWD = 0.2; Fig 1c) and a $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ mean age of 76.5 ± 6.8 Ma (95% conf., MSWD = 0.20) using GJ1 zircon as the primary SRM. With YGX2113 as the primary SRM, we obtained an intercept age of 80 ± 13 Ma (MSWD = 1.2) and a $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ mean age

79.0±6.8 Ma (95% conf., MSWD = 0.079; Fig. 1d). This age aligns well with the U-Pb zircon age previously reported for the Polski Gradets granodiorite, dated at 78.27±0.18 Ma (Georgiev et al., 2012).

Conclusions

The optimized analytical conditions enabled us to obtain reliable age data for wolframites from the Barruecopardo (Western Spain) and Polski Gradets (Eastern Bulgaria) deposits, yielding ages of 315.2±5.3 Ma and 79.0±6.8 Ma, respectively. These results are in close agreement with the ages of the host granites and granodiorites, demonstrating the suitability of the applied technique for direct (*in situ*) dating of tungsten deposits by LA-ICP-MS, using wolframite SRMs, together with or as an alternative to zircon SRMs.

Acknowledgements: The study was supported by the AGEMERA project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement N 101058178. Logistical support and granted access to the open pit of the Barruecopardo mine, provided by Saloro SLU, are highly appreciated.

References

- Antona, J. F., A. Fallick, A. Garcia Sanchez. 1994. Fluid inclusion and stable isotope studies of gold-tungsten bearing hydrothermal deposits, Saucelle-Barruecopardo area, Spain. – *Europ. J. Mineral.*, 6, 819–835.
- Borrajó, I., F. Tornos, H. Stein. 2022. Re-Os evidence for diachronous W-Sn mineralization in Iberia (Spain and Portugal). – In: *Proceedings of 16th SGA Biennial Meeting*, 33–36.
- Deng, X.-D., T. Luo, J.-W. Li, Z.-C. Hu. 2019. Direct dating of hydrothermal tungsten mineralization using *in situ* wolframite U–Pb chronology by laser ablation ICP-MS. – *Chem. Geol.*, 515, 94–104; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2019.04.005>.
- Chiaradia, M., Schaltegger, U., Spikings, R., Wotzlaw, J.F., Ovtcharova, M., 2013. How accurately can we date the duration of magmatic-hydrothermal events in porphyry systems? – *Econom. Geol.*, 108, 565–584.
- Grohol, M., C. Veeh. 2023. *European Commission: Study on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU– Final Report*. Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, Publications Office of the European Union; <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/725585>.
- Georgiev, S., A. von Quadt, C. A. Heinrich, I. Peytcheva, P. Marchev. 2012. Time evolution of a rifted continental arc: Integrated ID-TIMS and LA-ICPMS study of magmatic zircons from the Eastern Srednogie, Bulgaria. – *Lithos*, 154, 53–67; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2012.06.020>.
- Kamenov, B., E. Tarassova. 1995. The Polskigradetz pluton from Eastern Bulgaria – petrology, geochemistry and ore mineralizations. – In: *Proceeding of the XV Congr., CBGA, Athens, Geol. Soc. Greece, Spec. Publ.*, 4, 2, 527–532.
- Nedjalkov, N. 1983. The wolframite mineralization at Polski Gradec, Sliven District. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 44, 3, 304–307 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).
- Stavrev, M., K. Popov, K. Ruskov, S. Chavdarova, A. Hikov, I. Peytcheva. 2021. Spatial distribution of the geochemical associations in the Babyak Mo-Ag-Au-W-Bi-base metal deposit, Western Rhodopes (Bulgaria): application of factor analysis. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 82, 3, 67–69; <https://doi.org/10.52215/rev.bgs.2021.82.3.67>.
- Tarassov, M., R. Iliev. 1992. Wolframite from an occurrence at the village of Polski Gradetz. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 53, 1, 11–16 (in Russian with English abstract).
- Tarassova, E., M. Tarassov, Yu. Christova. 1996. Hydrothermal metasomatites related to the Polski Gradetz pluton, Eastern Srednogie. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 57, 2, 69–74 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).
- Pohl, J. 2023. *Mineral Resource Estimation Barruecopardo Tungsten deposit, JORC Technical Report*, 153 p.
- Popov, P., K. Popov. 2022. *Metallogeny of Bulgaria (with a metallogenic map of Bulgaria on a scale 1:500 000)*. Sofia, BMGK Comers Ltd., 426 p. (in Bulgarian with extended English abstract).
- Virmond, A. L., J. F. Wotzlaw, R. Rojas-Arancibia, D. Selby, C. Chelle-Michou. 2024. Multi-million-year magmatic and hydrothermal activity is key to the formation of supergiant to behemothian porphyry copper deposits. – *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.*, 179, 88, 1–17; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-024-02167-4>.
- Yang, M., Y. H. Yang, S. T. Wu, R. L. Romer, X. D. Che, Z. F. Zhao, Y. Li, W. Jin-Hui, F. Y. Xie, L. W. Huang, C. Zhang, D. Zhang, Y. Zhang. 2020. Accurate and precise *in situ* U-Pb isotope dating of wolframite series minerals via LA-SF-ICP-MS. – *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 35, 2191–2203; <https://doi.org/10.1039/DOJA00248H>.